

LINGVOCULTURAL INTERFERENCE IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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This article deals with the influence of the native language on learning a foreign language and overcoming its interfering aspects. Based on the analysis of domestic and foreign methodological literature, the author identifies the following types of linguocultural interference: phonological, grammatical, lexical, syntactic and sociocultural. To overcome interference, a special set of exercises is required to ensure maximum weakening of the effects of the identified types of interference.

Key words: interlinguistic, communicative competence, lingvoculture, target language, Nowadays, it is not enough to be a good specialist in a particular field of activity. Thanks to the development of globalization that is increasing every day, proficiency in at least one foreign language is becoming a necessary condition in order to represent oneself on the international labor market. That is why in the modern world more and more people are starting to learn foreign languages.

The main objectives of teaching a foreign language include mastering linguistic competence, or the ability to speak without errors. It is known that one of the main indicators of the level of proficiency in a foreign language is the degree of correctness of foreign language speech.

However, the practice of teaching foreign languages, as well as methodological research data, indicate that mastering foreign language means of communication is complicated by the interfering influence of the native language, which generates not only interlinguistic, but also discursive and socio-cultural interference in intercultural communication. The low level of foreign language speech skills is explained by the lack of targeted and systematic work on vocabulary, grammar and phonetics, which are susceptible to interference. The principle of taking into account the native language is one of the main principles of teaching foreign languages. This principle is based on two opposite trends, which can be conditionally characterized as positive and negative. We are talking about the principles of transfer and interference. If in the process of learning a foreign language we can bring certain parallels with our native language and establish general patterns, then the learning process will present fewer difficulties.

The positive influence of the native language on the formation of similar language and speech skills is called transfer. At any level of learning a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account not only the linguistic side of the problem, but also those skills that the student can transfer from his native language to a foreign language. That is why in modern language concepts such great attention is paid to the integration of approaches to teaching native and foreign languages, as well as other humanitarian disciplines.

However, when studying a foreign language, we often encounter linguistic phenomena that either have no analogues in our native language or are used completely differently. In this case, a negative interference phenomenon occurs. The nature of the occurrence of interference is described in the studies of many methodological scientists. When forming secondary language competence, new lexico-grammatical phenomena are usually translated by students into their native language, the presence or absence of phonetic, lexical-

grammatical, and semantic types of correspondence with their native language is analyzed. This does not happen by chance, since the specifics of the interaction of contacting languages, as a rule, comes down to two types of processes: intralinguistic and interlinguistic.

Intralinguistic processes take place within one language system; in the case of over-generalization, this is an irrelevant transfer of phenomena from the native language to a foreign language to which they are not characteristic.

Interlinguistic processes give rise to the greatest difficulties in mastering a foreign language and give rise to typical multi-level errors that can only be eliminated using a specially designed system of exercises. Also, interlingual interference is due to the divergence of linguistic and cultural pictures of the world among different ethnic groups, differences in their encyclopedic and linguistic knowledge, and regional competence, i.e., the influence of the native language on the foreign language being studied, which is explicated in the form of speech errors, violation of language norms and unreasonable transposition of the phenomena of one language into another, resulting in a violation of the norms of another language structure. The reason for the occurrence of interference is the fact that a person constructs his foreign language utterance according to the norms of his native language and establishes unusual connections and relationships between individual linguistic facts of a foreign language.

Taking into account interference when learning a foreign language allows you to prevent errors, reduce their number, and thereby facilitate and intensify the learning process. Errors can become a serious obstacle when communicating with foreigners, and some signal a lack of knowledge not only of the language, but also of its culture. If the teacher's attention is paid to eliminating such errors, then teaching a foreign language will be more effective. Thus, interference is "an unconscious, automatic transfer of linguistic properties of the native language into a foreign one, it can manifest itself at all levels - from morphological to discursive and means unconventional expression and a violation of textuality"

Classifying the types of interference allows us to identify and overcome the phenomena of interference at the early stages at the phonological, grammatical, lexical, syntactic and socio-cultural levels.

Overcoming interference is carried out through the formation of missing knowledge, "building on" the missing ones and correcting distorted knowledge through:

- purposeful selection of texts that reflect the linguistic, sociocultural and communicative-behavioral specifics of a foreign language society,
- creation of a model for overcoming interference at different stages of learning a foreign language;
- development of a system of exercises and tasks to overcome interfering phenomena of an inter- and extralinguistic nature.

The main aim of teaching a foreign language at school and higher education is to ensure that students master communicative competence, the most important component of which is linguistic competence. However, experience shows that interference that arises in intercultural communication often occurs not only due to distortions of linguistic norms, but also as a consequence of interfering phenomena, namely linguistic and sociocultural interference, which are understood respectively as communicative behavior and background knowledge of representatives of a foreign cultural community.

Thus, both students and teachers must not only be familiar with the phenomena of interference and their causes, but also must know how to overcome them. For high-quality overcoming and prevention, a whole set of exercises is required, including an optimal set of necessary types and types of exercises, the implementation of which in sufficient quantity and in a certain sequence ensures maximum weakening of the effect of phonological, grammatical and lexical interference.

References:

1. Баграмова Н.В. Лингводидактические основы обучения второму ино-странному языку: Монография. – СПб., 2010. – 230 с.
2. Балясникова Н.С. Оптимизация обучения лексике английского языка. как второго иностранного студентов языковых вузов (английский язык при первом иностранном языке – испанском): Автореферат дис. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.02. – СПб., 2009. – 23 с.
3. Барышникова Ю.В. О профилактике лексической интерференции при обучении английскому языку // Номо Loquens: актуальные вопросы лингвистики и методики преподавания иностранных языков сборник научных статей / Под редакцией И.Ю. Щемелевой. – СПб., 2013. – С. 239–245.
4. Вторушина Ю.Л. Формирование иноязычной культурной картины мира в контексте профессиональной подготовки учителей иностранного языка // Науч-ные исследования в образовании. – 2006. – №6. – С. 39–40.
5. Павлова Л.В. Развитие личности в контексте диалога культур // Профес-сиональное образование. Столица. – 2010. – №1. – С. 40–41.